

Supplementary Table 1 – Levels baseline and 12 months post-surgery for hypercalcemic men

Variable	Baseline	1 month	3 months	6 months	12 months	P-value
	Mean (SD)					
Total Calcium (mmol/L)	2.62 (0.20)	2.57 (0.21)	2.54 (0.23)	2.53 (0.17)	2.53 (0.10)	0.771
Ionized Calcium (mmol/L)	1.48 (0.16)	1.38 (0.13)	1.37 (0.12)	1.32 (0.14)	1.33 (0.03)	0.041
Albumin (g/L)	37 (4)	36 (5)	36 (4)	37 (4)	38 (3)	0.540
PTH (pmol/L)	1.2 (1.2)	2.0 (1.5)	2.0 (1.2)	2.3 (1.3)	2.1 (1.5)	0.045
25(OH)D (nmol/L)	50 (18)	52 (18)	53 (21)	52 (23)	51 (18)	0.923
1,25(OH) ₂ D ₃ (pmol/L)	138.1 (66.4)	100.5 (23.7)	93.7 (19.2)	123.8 (58.4)	131.3 (40.0)	0.536
Ferritin (µg/L)	247.0 (206.0)	214.2 (123.8)	241.7 (212.4)	228.2 (142.6)	199.0 (213.0)	0.048
IL-2R (kU/L)	739.8 (367.6)	758.5 (341.5)	742.3 (368.6)	744.3 (201.9)	690.6 (325.7)	0.162
ACE (U/L)	113.7 (43.9)	108.3 (25.7)	103.9 (12.6)	99.3 (13.8)	122.2 (34.2)	0.540
eGFR	60.7 (22.4)	62.8 (30.1)	63.68 (31.7)	55.2 (27.3)	54.0 (23.9)	0.350

Legend Table 2B: PTH: parathyroid hormone; 25(OH)D: 25-hydroxyvitamin D; 1,25(OH)₂D₃: 1,25-dihydroxy vitamin D₃; IL-2R: Interleukine 2 receptor; ACE: peptidyl dipeptidase; eGFR: estimated glomerular filtration rate. Significance levels; p<0.05 by a linear mixed model for repeated measurements.

Supplementary Table 2 – Levels baseline and 12 months post-surgery for normocalcemic men

Variable	Baseline	1 month	3 months	6 months	12 months	P-value
	Mean (SD)					
Total Calcium (mmol/L)	2.36 (0.07)	2.31 (0.06)	2.39 (0.08)	2.38 (0.09)	2.40 (0.12)	0.144
Ionized Calcium (mmol/L)	1.23 (0.04)	1.22 (0.04)	1.25 (0.04)	1.25 (0.03)	1.24 (0.08)	0.550
Albumin (g/L)	41 (3)	38 (4)	41 (3)	40 (3)	40 (3)	0.536
PTH (pmol/L)	2.4 (1.1)	3.1 (1.4)	2.3 (1.4)	1.7 (1.1)	2.7 (1.9)	0.308
25(OH)D (nmol/L)	36 (17)	35 (19)	41 (23)	47 (20)	41 (20)	0.546
1,25(OH) ₂ D ₃ (pmol/L)	119.9 (60.0)	84.7 (21.3)	129.7 (11.3)	156.2 (46.1)	122.3 (76.3)	0.318
Ferritin (µg/L)	383.5 (243.2)	282.6 (155.3)	184.1 (105.6)	238.8 (146.4)	309.7 (46.5)	0.025
IL-2R (kU/L)	712.6 (406.5)	543.3 (234.0)	586.9 (221.4)	556.5 (214.2)	550.0 (104.7)	0.499
ACE (U/L)	118.2 (45.1)	113.8 (42.3)	111.0 (33.9)	121.4 (59.7)	109.4 (34.9)	0.901
eGFR	87.1 (9.5)	89.8 (7.4)	93.1 (12.5)	86.6 (8.7)	92.7 (6.7)	0.404

Legend Table 2A: PTH: parathyroid hormone; 25(OH)D: 25-hydroxyvitamin D; 1,25(OH)₂D₃: 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D; IL-2R: Interleukine 2 receptor; ACE: peptidyl dipeptidase; eGFR: estimated glomerular filtration rate. Significance levels; p<0.05 by a linear mixed model for repeated measurements.

Supplementary Table 3 – Questionnaire

Questionnaire	Scale
Your overall happiness with your surgery	(1-10)
Your pain now compared to before surgery <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VAS-score before surgery • VAS-score now 	(a lot worse / worse / the same / better / a lot better) (1-10) (1-10)
Your other symptoms now compared to before surgery?	(a lot worse / worse / the same / better / a lot better)
Your quality of life now compared to before surgery?	(a lot worse / worse / the same / better / a lot better)
If you had the choice, based on your experience, would you have done the surgery again?	(yes / no)

Legend Supplemental Table 1: Overview of the 5 questions the patients answered during the telephone interview. VAS-score = Visual Analog Scale where a higher score indicates greater pain intensity.